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REGULATIONS ARE POWERFUL THAN STRATEGY: INSTITUTIONAL INERTIA OF ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract: *In modern organizations, strategy often plays a symbolic role, declaring the desired direction but not defining actual management practices [5,14]. Actual management is reproduced through a stable system of regulations, procedures, and instructions that have a stronger influence on decisions, responsibility, and acceptable behavior than any strategic documents [1,2].*

The article analyzes the phenomenon of institutional inertia, in which regulations dominate strategy not because of incompetence or sabotage, but because of the organization's architecture [13,22]. Regulations act as carriers of organizational memory [23,25], reduce uncertainty [2,19], and ensure the legitimacy of decisions [1,10], forming a "zone of permissibility" within which strategy can exist only if it does not violate procedural stability [14].

Particular attention is paid to the post-Soviet context, where regulations have historically served as a tool for protecting against errors, personal risks, and external instability. Strategy, however, is perceived as a source of uncertainty and personal responsibility, which contradicts the culture of control and safety nets [9,21].

It has been shown that overcoming inertia requires transforming strategy into a tool for changing institutional rules: revising regulations, redistributing mandates, and changing decision-making mechanisms [4,17]. Without this, strategy remains a declaration, and the organization imitates change while maintaining the same functional logic [14].

Key words: *institutional inertia, strategy, regulations, organizational memory, post-Soviet management, formalization of processes*

In management practice, strategy is traditionally viewed as the highest form of management intent, setting the direction of an organization's development and determining resource allocation priorities [5,7,8]. However, in real work, the influence of strategy on day-to-day decisions turns out to be significantly weaker than assumed in classical models [14].

Experience shows that managers are guided primarily by regulations, instructions, and established procedures, even when they conflict with strategic goals [1,2]. Decisions are made not based on the logic of strategic feasibility, but rather on the logic of "what is permissible," "what is prescribed," and "what does not create risks" [10, 19].

This gap cannot be explained solely by resistance to change or communication failures. It reflects a deeper institutional problem [13,22]. Regulations serve as a safeguard against uncertainty, responsibility, and external sanctions [2,19], creating a stable framework for governance [1].

This phenomenon is particularly evident in the post-Soviet space, where regulations have historically served as a key instrument of managerial stability [9]. In conditions of high uncertainty and weak institutions of trust, it was regulations that minimized the consequences of errors and redistributed risks from individual managers to the system [21].

Strategy and regulations find themselves in an unequal relationship: the former declares change, while the latter reproduces stability [14]. As a result, strategic management is often replaced by an imitation of change [14].

The purpose of the study is to analyze the reasons and mechanisms of the dominance of regulations over strategy, as well as to identify the institutional conditions under which strategy can become a real management tool [4,17].

This study was conducted within the framework of a qualitative analytical approach and is aimed at identifying institutional mechanisms [13,22]. The theoretical basis was provided by the provisions of institutional theory [13,22], organizational theory [6,10] and strategic management [5,7,8]. The empirical basis consisted of generalized observations of management practices in large organizations in the post-Soviet space.

In classical theory, strategy is viewed as a tool for purposeful change in organizational logic [5,7,15]. It involves revising the principles of resource allocation, decision-making, and performance evaluation [8]. Strategic decisions, by their very nature, cannot be fully regulated, as they rely on assumptions about the future [2].

However, as strategic management becomes institutionalized, strategy is increasingly formalized in the form of formalized documents embedded in the existing system of regulations [14]. As a result, it loses the ability to change organizational logic [14].

In classical management theory, strategy is viewed not simply as a set of long-term goals or development plans, but as a tool for purposefully changing organizational logic. In this sense, strategy is intended to go beyond current operational activities and establish new principles for resource allocation, decision-making, and performance evaluation. It not only sets the direction of movement but also entails reconsidering how the organization operates, what practices it considers acceptable, and what management assumptions it accepts as fundamental.

In the original theoretical model, strategy serves as a mechanism for breaking with the inertia of the past. It is focused on transforming established management patterns, reconfiguring processes, and changing the roles of key actors. This is why strategy, in the classical sense, is always associated with uncertainty, risk, and the need for management choices that go beyond formalized procedures. Strategic decisions, by their very nature, cannot be fully regulated, as they rely on assumptions about the future, which have not yet been structured by rules and regulations.

However, as strategic management becomes institutionalized in large organizations, its function gradually shifts. Strategy is increasingly expressed in the form of formalized documents, programs, and indicators embedded within the existing regulatory system. As a result, it loses the ability to change organizational logic and begins to reproduce it in a more complex, but essentially unchanging form. Strategic goals are formulated in such a way as to avoid revising basic procedures, and strategic initiatives are tailored to existing regulatory constraints.

In this context, strategy ceases to be a source of institutional change and becomes a superstructure on top of the existing management architecture. It begins to serve as a symbolic confirmation of development, without affecting the underlying mechanisms of decision-making and responsibility allocation. The organization formally declares forward movement, but in fact maintains previous modes of action, adapting its strategic language to established practices.

It's crucial to emphasize that this distortion of the role of strategy isn't the result of a misinterpretation of theory or a lack of managerial expertise. It reflects a structural contradiction between strategy as an instrument of change and the organization as a system oriented toward stability and predictability. The more complex and formalized an organization becomes, the greater the likelihood that strategy will be integrated into the existing logic rather than transforming it.

Regulations consolidate accumulated management practices and transform them into a "norm" of organizational action [1,23]. They become carriers of organizational memory [23,25], allowing for the reproduction of familiar models regardless of changes in leadership or external conditions [19].

Regulations acquire particular significance in conditions of uncertainty: they minimize the space for individual choice and redistribute responsibility to the system [2,10].

In management systems, regulations are traditionally viewed as an auxiliary tool, ensuring order, repeatability, and predictability of activities. According to classical management logic, they should serve strategy, translating strategic decisions into operational procedures and reducing variability in execution. However, in real organizational practice, regulations often go beyond a technical function and become an independent institution, defining acceptable forms of management behavior.

Regulations play a key stabilizing role, consolidating accumulated management practices and turning them into a "norm" for organizational action. Through procedures, instructions, and rules, an organization captures past experience, including both successful decisions and ways to avoid mistakes. In this sense, regulations become carriers of organizational memory, allowing the system to reproduce familiar management models regardless of leadership changes, strategic priorities, or external conditions.

Regulations are particularly important in conditions of uncertainty and increased risk. Formalized procedures minimize the scope for individual choice, redistributing responsibility from a specific manager to the system as a whole. A decision made "according to the regulations" is institutionally protected, even if its effectiveness in a specific situation is questionable. Thus, regulations serve to reduce management risks, acting as a kind of shield between the manager and the potential consequences of deviating from the established procedure.

Over time, regulations begin not only to stabilize processes but also to reproduce a certain management logic. They shape the understanding of what is considered the right decision, an acceptable action, and a legitimate basis for management choice. As a result, the procedure itself becomes a criterion of rationality, and compliance with regulations becomes a substitute for assessing management results. The organization begins to be managed not so much by goals and meanings as by adherence to rules.

It's important to note that the increasing role of regulations isn't a consequence of bureaucratic excess per se. In most cases, it's an organization's rational response to the complexity, scale, and heterogeneity of processes. The larger the system, the greater the need for standardization and formalization. However, it's precisely at this point that regulations begin to take on an inertial nature, establishing not only order but also restrictions on change.

Regulations serve a dual function. On the one hand, they ensure the stability, controllability, and reproducibility of processes. On the other, they consolidate established practices and restrain attempts to change organizational logic. In this capacity, regulations become a key element of institutional inertia, with which strategy inevitably conflicts.

A persistent institutional tension develops between strategy (focused on change) and regulations (focused on stabilization) [13,14]. Strategy requires room for choice and experimentation, while procedural reality minimizes variability [1,2]. Comparing the roles of strategy and regulations in a management system reveals a fundamental contradiction between the strategic intent and the procedural reality of an organization. Strategy, by its nature, is oriented toward change, development, and moving beyond the current state, while regulations aim to consolidate already mastered practices and maintain controllability. As a result, a structural tension develops between them that is not temporary or accidental, but has a persistent institutional character.

Strategic design presupposes a space for managerial choice, allowing for experimentation, adjustment, and decision-making under conditions of uncertainty. However, the procedural reality of an organization is structured to minimize variability and reduce the number of situations requiring individual judgment. Regulations predefine permissible actions, the sequence of steps, and criteria for correctness, thereby limiting the possibility of implementing strategic initiatives that go beyond the established order.

In practice, this contradiction manifests itself in the fact that strategy is declared a priority, but when faced with specific management situations, it takes a backseat to regulations. Managers are forced to choose not between what is strategically expedient and what is inexpedient, but between what is regulatoryly acceptable and what is regulatoryly risky. Even when recognizing the

discrepancy between procedures and strategic goals, preference is given to actions that ensure institutional protection and predictability of consequences.

As a result, strategy begins to adapt to procedural reality, rather than the other way around. Strategic goals are formulated in such a way as to avoid requiring revisions to key regulations, and strategic initiatives are implemented as formal projects that do not affect the core decision-making mechanisms. Strategy gradually transforms into a set of corrective measures compatible with the existing system of rules but unable to alter its logic.

This contradiction is exacerbated by the fact that procedures enjoy a high degree of legitimacy within the organization. They are perceived as an objective and neutral basis for action, whereas strategy is associated with a subjective management intent dependent on specific individuals and time priorities. In this logic, regulations become a "hard" management reality, while strategy is a variable subject to interpretation and mitigation.

Over time, any organization accumulates its own management experience—not in the form of strategies and presentations, but in the form of habitual ways of operating. This experience forms what can be called organizational memory: tacit knowledge about how decisions are actually made, what is considered right and what is considered dangerous. It is this memory that shapes everyday management practices much more powerfully than official documents [23,25].

Organizational memory consists of repeated management decisions that once worked, or at least did not lead to negative consequences. If a certain course of action helped avoid problems, sanctions, or conflicts, it becomes ingrained and begins to be reproduced automatically. Over time, such decisions become the rules, instructions, and common sense of the organization, even if external conditions have changed.

It's important to understand that this memory preserves not the best practices, but the safest ones. The organization primarily remembers what reduced risks for the system and its managers. Therefore, many regulations reflect not the optimal way of working, but rather a method that minimizes liability and uncertainty. Any strategy that requires going beyond these familiar scenarios is perceived as potentially dangerous, even if it is logically sound.

Organizational memory is transmitted through daily managerial socialization. New managers quickly learn not so much the content of strategy as the actual rules of the game: where initiative is allowed, and where it's best to strictly follow instructions; which decisions are rewarded, and which create problems. In this process, strategy remains in the background, while practical guidelines are formed through observing the behavior of colleagues and the system's reactions.

As a result, organizational memory begins to filter strategic initiatives. Those ideas that fit within familiar logic and don't require a revision of regulations receive support. The rest are either formally accepted but not implemented, or transformed into a safe and harmless form. Thus, strategy adapts to past experience rather than setting a new direction for development.

This is why organizational memory is one of the main sources of institutional inertia. It helps an organization maintain stability and control, but simultaneously limits its ability to make real changes. Until a strategy addresses accumulated management practices and associated regulations, it remains a declaration, incapable of changing the actual logic of management.

Organizational regulations are rarely created for the sake of convenience or efficiency alone. They arise primarily as a way to reduce management risks—for the system as a whole and for individual managers. Clearly defined rules allow for the definition in advance of which actions are considered acceptable and which are not, thereby reducing uncertainty and individual responsibility [2,19].

In everyday management practice, regulations serve a protective function. A decision made in accordance with the instructions is considered correct simply because it complies with the rules, even if the outcome is far from optimal. In this logic, what's more important is not what was done, but rather that it was done "as expected." This allows managers and employees to protect themselves from claims, audits, and subsequent litigation.

The higher the level of external and internal control, the more the organization relies on regulations. They become a form of collective insurance against errors, redistributing responsibility from individual managers to a system of rules. As a result, decision-making shifts from assessing the situation to verifying compliance with procedures: the priority is not to violate regulations, but to achieve the best possible result.

In such an environment, strategic decisions that require deviation from established procedures are perceived as a source of increased risk. Even if a strategy is formally approved, its implementation often requires actions for which there are no ready-made instructions. This automatically makes the strategy less attractive to managers, as it takes them outside the zone of procedural protection.

Gradually, regulations are beginning to replace management thinking. Instead of analyzing goals and consequences, decisions are made based on the principle of least risk. Strategy is transformed into a set of formal measures that can be incorporated into existing instructions without changing their essence. Thus, regulations become not just a management tool, but the primary criterion of rationality and safety.

As a result, regulations do reduce management risks, but at the cost of strategic flexibility. The organization maintains stability and predictability, but loses the ability to act outside predetermined scenarios. This is where their dual role manifests itself: they protect the system but simultaneously limit its development.

In real management practice, a decision is considered justified not when it is consistent with strategy, but when it can be defended procedurally. The legitimacy of management actions is formed primarily through compliance with regulations, approvals, and formal requirements. Strategy, in this case, serves as a secondary argument, rarely valid on its own without support from procedure [1,10,14].

Procedures allow a management decision to be formally correct, even if its connection to strategic goals is unclear. Approval, signature, reference to regulations, or internal orders create a sense of correctness and finality. In this logic, managerial responsibility is replaced by procedural responsibility: what matters is not the outcome of the decision, but that it passed all the established stages.

Strategy, unlike procedures, lacks the same level of institutional protection. It rarely provides unambiguous answers and requires interpretation, choice, and personal responsibility. Therefore, in controversial situations, managers instinctively rely not on strategic formulations, but on regulations that can be presented as the formal basis for their actions. Procedure becomes a source of legitimacy, and strategy—a backdrop for explanations.

Over time, this leads to a shift in management focus. The question of "is the decision consistent with strategy?" gives way to "is it procedurally compliant." Even strategically significant initiatives begin to be assessed through the prism of formal requirements: approvals, reporting, and meeting deadlines, rather than through their actual impact on the organization's development.

As a result, strategy gradually loses its status as a management tool and becomes a rhetorical resource. It is used to justify existing procedural decisions, but not to formulate them. The management system begins to reproduce itself through procedures, and strategy serves this reproducing logic without disrupting its stability.

Legitimizing decisions through procedures is a key mechanism of institutional inertia. Until strategy is integrated into a system of formal legitimization—regulations, decision-making rules, and the distribution of responsibility—it cannot compete with procedures and inevitably loses out to them in actual management practice.

In most organizations, strategy formally exists but lacks any real managerial power. It is approved, agreed upon, and presented as a development guideline, but lacks the institutional mandate to change decision-making rules. Strategy declares goals but lacks an enforcement mechanism comparable to regulations and procedures [4,17].

An institutional mandate in management means the right and opportunity to influence the system's behavior: to revise rules, redistribute powers, and allow deviations from the established

order. Regulations possess such a mandate—violating them entails consequences. Strategy, however, often does not provide a manager with a formal basis for going beyond the procedure, even if it is necessary to achieve strategic goals. As a result, strategy becomes a symbolic document without any real leverage.

In practice, this translates into the preference for the latter when strategy and regulations clash. A manager can cite regulations, but rarely can they cite strategy as sufficient justification for an unconventional decision. Strategy does not protect against audits, does not absolve personal responsibility, and does not guarantee institutional support. Therefore, it is used as an explanatory rather than a determining factor in management.

The lack of an institutional mandate means that strategy adapts to the existing system rather than changing behavior. Its formulations become vague, open to any procedural interpretation. Strategic initiatives are framed in such a way as to avoid revising key regulations, and their implementation is reduced to the formal implementation of measures that do not affect basic governance mechanisms.

It's important to emphasize that this situation isn't the result of a weak strategy or the insufficient skills of its developers. It reflects a structural imbalance between the strategic level and the regulatory environment. Until strategy is integrated into the system of authority and responsibility, it cannot compete with regulations for influence on management decisions.

A strategy without an institutional mandate inevitably becomes a mere declaration. It creates the illusion of purposeful development without changing the actual logic of management. It is precisely in this form that strategy is most convenient for an organization: it demonstrates forward movement without disrupting the stability and predictability of the existing regulatory system.

When a strategy lacks an institutional mandate, an organization finds a compromise: it begins to formally implement the strategy without changing the actual management logic. This creates the phenomenon of imitation strategic change—a situation in which the external signs of transformation are present, but the internal mechanisms remain the same.

The formalization of execution manifests itself primarily in the project and reporting framework. Programs, roadmaps, working groups, KPIs, and presentations are created to support the strategy. Activity is recorded in reports and statuses, but this activity does not affect regulations, the distribution of authority, or decision-making rules. The strategy is implemented as a set of measures, not as a change in the institutional environment.

In this model, the key focus is not on the outcome of strategic changes, but on their proper execution. The success of a strategy is assessed by the availability of documents, adherence to deadlines, and the formal implementation of plans. If a project is closed according to regulations, it is considered completed, even if management practices remain unchanged. Strategy becomes a managed reporting process, not a transformation tool.

Imitation is enhanced by its institutional safety. Formal strategy execution requires no overstepping of procedures and poses no personal risks for managers. On the contrary, it demonstrates loyalty to the strategic course while fully adhering to regulations. As a result, the system rewards not those who genuinely change their ways of working, but those who best adapt the strategic language to existing rules.

A sustainable management practice is gradually emerging, in which strategy is perceived as a mandatory but externally supported layer. Actual decisions continue to be made within a procedural logic, while strategic changes exist in the form of reporting structures. This creates a "dual reality" effect: at the document level, the organization is transformed, while at the behavioral level, it reproduces itself.

Formalizing execution and simulating change are not a random distortion, but a rational adaptation of the organization to the contradiction between strategy and regulations. As long as strategy does not require a redesign of procedures or alter the criteria for decision legitimacy, imitation becomes the most sustainable and least risky way for the system to "implement" strategic initiatives.

In a context where regulations define the permissible boundaries of management actions, managers inevitably adapt their behavior to the regulatory environment. This adaptation is not individual but systemic and is formed as a rational survival strategy within the organizational logic. Managers learn to act in a way that minimizes risks, maintains control, and avoids situations in which their decisions may be called into question.

A key element of this adaptation is shifting the focus from achieving strategic goals to adhering to procedures. Managers focus less on the question of "what needs to be done for development" and more on "what can be done without breaking the rules." Even when understanding the strategic feasibility of certain steps, preference is given to actions that can be formally justified through regulations, approvals, or established practices.

Over time, this leads to a transformation in management thinking. Initiative begins to be viewed as a potential source of problems, and deviation from procedure as an unjustified risk. Management competence is increasingly associated not with the ability to make decisions under uncertainty, but with the ability to navigate a system of rules and correctly construct formal processes. Strategy is perceived as a general guideline that does not require direct management action.

Behavioral adaptation is reinforced through a system of evaluation and rewards. The organization rewards managers who demonstrate stability, predictability, and the absence of disruption, rather than those who initiate real change. This results in a layer of managers who are effectively integrated into the regulatory environment but have limited capacity for strategic thinking and transformational action.

In post-Soviet organizations, regulations were initially developed not as a management service, but as a tool for the system's survival. They emerged in conditions of high uncertainty, strict external control, and the personal responsibility of managers for any deviations from established procedures. In such an environment, regulations were not abstract rules but concrete protection—a way to demonstrate that a decision was made "correctly" and "according to instructions" [9,21].

In practice, regulations served as a stabilizer in situations where strategic thinking was secondary to plan execution, compliance with regulations, and preventing failures. Leaders were evaluated not by their ability to change the system, but by their ability to ensure its smooth operation. Regulations allowed for predictable action, reduced the likelihood of errors, and created a sense of control even in the face of resource shortages and constant external constraints.

This logic became deeply ingrained in management culture. Regulations came to be perceived as a source of order and fairness: if the rules were the same for everyone, then management was considered correct. Any deviation from procedure was interpreted as a potential threat to the system, even if it was rationally justified. As a result, initiative and autonomy were long perceived not as managerial qualities, but as a risk.

It's important to note that in unstable conditions, regulations still serve a useful function. They help keep the system from descending into chaos, provide a minimum level of control, and protect the organization from sudden fluctuations. However, problems arise when regulations become an end in themselves, rather than a tool, and maintaining them becomes more important than development.

In post-Soviet management practice, regulations serve not just as rules but as a source of managerial legitimacy. A decision is considered "correct" not because it produced the desired result or is consistent with strategy, but because it was made in accordance with the established procedure. It is regulations that grant the manager the right to act and simultaneously serve as protection against potential claims.

In practice, this manifests itself quite simply: if a decision is properly formalized, coordinated, and based on instructions, it is perceived as legitimate, regardless of its effectiveness. If the outcome is negative, attention shifts from the substance of the decision to the correctness of the procedure. If no violations are identified, responsibility is diffused, and the management decision is considered justified. In this sense, regulations replace the criterion of management quality.

The regulations also serve as a universal language of legitimation. They are understood by all system participants—management, controllers, auditors, and inspection bodies. Reference to the

regulations requires no additional explanation or interpretation. Unlike a strategy, which is open to various interpretations, regulations are perceived as an objective and neutral guideline, independent of specific management figures.

Over time, this leads to an institutional shift: management begins to be structured around procedures rather than goals. Regulations become the fulcrum for decision-making, the distribution of responsibility, and the evaluation of management performance. Strategy, meanwhile, is used post-factum—to explain decisions already made or to give them meaning.

Regulations as a source of managerial legitimacy complete the formation of institutional inertia. As long as the legitimacy of decisions is determined by procedure rather than strategic intent, strategy cannot become a real management tool. It remains a declaration, while regulations continue to define the boundaries of what is possible and acceptable in management practice.

To understand the reasons for the dominance of regulations over strategy in post-Soviet organizations, it is necessary to consider historically established management attitudes and practices. Table 1 systematizes the key institutional factors that shape the persistent inertia of management behavior.

Table 1 - Post-Soviet sources of institutional inertia of governance

Factor	How it was formed historically	How it manifests itself in practice today	Impact on strategy
Regulations as the basis of management	Regulations are a tool for the system's survival in conditions of shortages and control.	Decisions are made "according to the instructions," even if they are outdated	Strategy gives way to procedure
Risk mitigation culture	Mistake = sanction, not experience	Leaders avoid unconventional solutions	Strategy is perceived as a threat
Lack of trust in managerial autonomy	Initiative was associated with deviation from the line	Even obvious steps require coordination	The strategy is losing its responsiveness
Personalized responsibility	Responsibility without real authority	The manager defends himself with regulations	Strategy does not become the basis for action
Procedural legitimacy	"Correct" = "according to the rules"	The main thing is correct design	The strategy is used post factum
Hierarchical trust model	Trust only from the top down	Low levels lack initiative	The strategy is not being implemented
The historical role of control	Control is more important than results	The report is more important than the effect	A simulation of changes occurs
Sustainability is more important than development	Maintaining the system is a priority	Any changes are "blurred"	Strategy becomes a symbol

Regulation as a protection of the individual	The regulations reduced personal risks	A solution without regulations = dangerous	Initiative is being squeezed out
Inherited management logic	Transmission of practices, meanings	New managers adapt not quickly	Strategy does not change behavior

The factors presented demonstrate that institutional inertia is the result of the long historical development of a management logic in which regulations served a stabilizing and protective function. Under these conditions, strategy could not become a fully-fledged management tool and was relegated to the declarative realm.

The key mistake of most strategic initiatives is that strategy is perceived as a set of goals, indicators, and development directions, while actual management decisions continue to be made according to the old rules. In this configuration, strategy inevitably loses out to regulations, since it does not intervene in the decision-making mechanism itself. Breaking institutional inertia is only possible if strategy begins to change the rules, rather than simply supplement them with new formulations [4,17].

In practice, this means that strategy must directly influence the regulatory environment. Strategic priorities must be recognized as the basis for revising procedures, simplifying approvals, and allowing for managerial deviations. If strategy does not formally grant managers the right to act differently from the regulations, it is incapable of changing the system's behavior. In this sense, strategy should become the source of new rules of the game, not an add-on to existing ones.

The first practical step is recognizing that not all regulations are neutral. Some of them reinforce past management logic and directly impede strategic change. Therefore, the strategy should include not only development goals but also a list of regulatory restrictions subject to revision or temporary suspension. This shifts the strategy from a declarative to an institutional level.

The second step involves redistributing management authority. Strategy must be supported by the right to make decisions outside standard procedures within predefined zones. Such zones of strategic autonomy allow managers to act within the logic of development without fear of procedural sanctions. It is important that this authority be formalized, otherwise the strategic initiative will again become vulnerable.

The third step is changing the logic of decision legitimization. Strategy must become an acceptable and sufficient basis for management actions, alongside regulations. This requires a revision of the evaluation and control system: management decisions must be assessed not only by their compliance with procedures but also by their contribution to strategic priorities. Without this, strategy will not be able to compete with regulations for influence on behavior.

Changing the role of strategy is impossible without rebuilding the regulatory environment. As long as regulations remain oriented toward the previous management logic, any strategy will either be ignored or adapted to a safe and formal level. Therefore, the practical solution to institutional inertia lies not in abolishing regulations, but in their purposeful transformation in line with strategic priorities.

The first principle of such a redesign is to reject the one-size-fits-all approach to regulations. In most organizations, rules are applied equally to all situations, regardless of their strategic significance. This deprives strategy of flexibility and inhibits initiative. Regulations must be differentiated: strategically significant processes require a different degree of formalization than routine operations. Where the organization is evolving, rules should not restrict but support change.

The second principle is built-in adaptability. Regulations should answer not only the question "how to do things," but also the question "when it's acceptable to do things differently." In practical management, this means the introduction of formalized exceptions, simplified procedures, and

accelerated decision-making processes for strategic initiatives. Such mechanisms legitimize deviations from standard rules and alleviate managers' fear of procedural violations.

The third principle is to review regulations based on their managerial meaning, not their formal compliance. Many procedures continue to exist because they were introduced, not because they truly support the organization's current goals. Strategy should trigger a review of regulations based on the criterion of whether a given rule contributes to achieving strategic priorities or merely reproduces managerial inertia.

It's important to emphasize that redesigning regulations isn't a one-time campaign or a document flow optimization project. It's a management decision to redistribute trust and responsibility. Regulations cease to be the sole source of legitimacy and become a tool to support strategy. This requires a change in attitude toward errors, experiments, and deviations from standard scenarios.

Even a redesigned strategy and adapted regulations will not produce sustainable results unless the fundamental institutional conditions of governance change. Institutional inertia is reproduced not by individual documents, but by the system of trust, accountability, and legitimization of decisions. Therefore, overcoming it requires not merely cosmetic adjustments, but a change in the governance architecture as a whole [13,22].

The first key condition is the redistribution of responsibility and authority. As long as a manager is accountable for the outcome but lacks the authority to change the rules, they will act with a mindset of minimal risk. Overcoming inertia is only possible when strategic responsibility is backed by the formal right to deviate from procedures within predetermined boundaries. Without this, strategy remains a moral imperative rather than a management tool.

The second condition is the institutionalization of trust. In most organizations, trust is personal and easily lost through error. Strategic change requires institutional trust, which allows for management experimentation within the strategic mandate. In this context, error is not seen as a violation, but as part of the management search, as long as it remains within the agreed-upon boundaries.

The third condition is changing management evaluation criteria. As long as a manager's effectiveness is measured by stability, the absence of violations, and the accuracy of reporting, regulations will dominate strategy. Strategy only begins to work when management decisions are evaluated based on their contribution to development, and not just on compliance with procedures. This requires a review of KPI, control, and internal audit systems.

The fourth condition is a clear managerial stance by senior management. Overcoming institutional inertia is impossible without demonstrating that strategy takes precedence over procedures in strategically significant matters. If senior management always sides with regulations in conflict situations, the system quickly picks up on this signal and reverts to its previous logic.

The institutional conditions for overcoming inertia are linked less to the quality of strategic documents than to the organization's willingness to change its own rules of legitimacy. Strategy begins to work only when it becomes part of the institutional structure, rather than an external description of the desired future. Otherwise, regulations inevitably continue to reproduce the past, regardless of stated strategic ambitions. (table 2).

Table 2 - Model of alignment of strategy and regulatory environment

Management element	Dominance of regulations (as is)	Strategic Alignment (as it should be)	Management effect
The role of strategy	Declaration, a guideline "for the future" that does not influence decisions	Reason for changing rules and procedures	Strategy begins to influence behavior

The role of regulations	Source of legitimacy and protection	Tool to support strategic priorities	Regulations are no longer blocking development
Decision making	Based on the principle of procedural security	According to the principle of strategic expediency within the given framework	The imitation of changes is reduced
Deviation from procedures	Perceived as a violation and a risk	Formally permitted in strategic zones	Management flexibility appears
Manager's responsibility	Personal responsibility without authority	Responsibility is backed by an institutional mandate	The quality of decisions is improving
Legitimization of decisions	Through compliance with regulations	Through contribution to strategic priorities + procedures	Management logic is changing
Attitude to mistakes	Error = violation	Error = valid management search element	Fear of initiative is reduced
Behavior of managers	Adapting to the rules, avoiding risk	Conscious choice within the framework of strategy	Strategic thinking is being formed
Implementation of the strategy	Formal, project-reporting	Institutionally embedded	The "double reality" disappears
System stability	Stability without development	Managed development without loss of stability	Balance of control and change

The analysis shows that the dominance of regulations over strategy is not a management error or a consequence of poor execution, but a natural consequence of the institutional structure of modern organizations. Regulations serve the function of stabilizing, mitigating risks, and legitimizing management decisions, while strategy, lacking a comparable institutional mandate, remains a declarative guideline. In this configuration, strategy does not shape management behavior but adapts to the existing procedural reality.

This gap is particularly evident in the post-Soviet governance context, where regulations have historically served as the primary source of governance and system security. The culture of procedural control, shaped over decades, has entrenched a distrust of strategic autonomy and initiative, making regulations the primary criterion of managerial legitimacy. As a result, strategy has become formally integrated into the system, without altering the underlying logic of decision-making.

The key conclusion of the study is that strategy without institutional support inevitably becomes a form of managerial self-deception. The organization continues to reproduce past practices while simultaneously declaring progress. The imitation of strategic change, the formalization of execution, and the behavioral adaptation of managers become the system's rational response to the contradiction between development and stability.

Overcoming institutional inertia is only possible by changing the role of strategy in the management architecture. Strategy must cease being a set of goals and indicators and become an

instrument for changing the rules: the regulatory environment, the distribution of authority, the mechanisms for legitimizing decisions, and the criteria for management evaluation. Only then will it acquire a real institutional mandate and the ability to influence organizational behavior.

The choice between strategy and regulations is false. The issue is not abandoning procedures, but reconfiguring them to meet development goals. As long as regulations remain stronger than strategy, an organization maintains control at the cost of losing its future. Strategic development begins when rules begin to serve goals, not replace them.

An example from management practice: when there is a strategy, but decisions are made according to regulations.

A large manufacturing organization has approved a strategy to improve operational efficiency and reduce costs. Strategic documents outline priorities: streamlining processes, reducing internal approvals, increasing the accountability of line managers, and shifting from formal control to performance management.

In practice, one of the department managers proposes an obvious solution: changing the procurement procedure for consumables for his section. The proposal is logical, economically sound, and fully aligns with the strategy—it reduces lead times, minimizes downtime, and lowers indirect costs. However, implementation requires a deviation from the current procurement regulations, which require multi-stage approvals and a fixed list of suppliers.

The manager brings the initiative up for discussion. There are no formal objections: the calculations are correct, the effect is clear, and it meets strategic goals. Nevertheless, no decision is made. The reasoning sounds familiar: "The regulations do not allow it," "This is not stipulated by the procedure", "If something goes wrong, personal responsibility will be taken", "It's easier to work according to the approved procedure".

Ultimately, the proposal is either postponed "pending a review of the regulations," which hasn't happened for years, or transformed into a formal pilot project with no real impact. The strategy remains in presentations, while real decisions continue to be made within the logic of procedural safety.

It's important that no one deliberately sabotages the strategy. Leaders act rationally within the existing system. Following regulations guarantees managerial security, while strategic initiative does not. In this situation, opting for regulations is not an expression of conservatism, but a form of adaptation to the institutional environment.

LITERATURE

1. Weber M. Economy and society. — M.: Canon-press, 1994.
2. Simon G. Administrative behavior. - M.: Economica, 1995.
3. March J., Olsen Y. Rethinking Institutions: The Organizational Foundations of Politics. Moscow: Idea-Press, 2003.
4. North D. Institutions, institutional changes and the functioning of the economy. - M.: Fund of the economic book "Beginnings", 1997.
5. Mintzberg G. Strategic Safari. — St. Petersburg: Piter, 2013.
6. Mintzberg G. Structure in a Fist: Creating an Effective Organization. — St. Petersburg: Piter, 2004.
7. Chandler A. Strategy and structure. — M.: Alpina Business Books, 2008.
8. Porter M. Competitive strategy. — M.: Alpina Business Books, 2016.
9. Scone M. Organizational culture and leadership. — St. Petersburg: Piter, 2011.
10. Barnard C. Functions of the manager. - M.: Economica, 2009.
11. Argyris K. Personality and organization. — M.: Infra-M, 2004.
12. Argyris K., Schön D. Organizational learning II. - M.: Alpina Publisher, 2017.
13. DiMaggio P., Powell W. New institutionalism in organizational analysis. —Moscow: Idea-Press, 2010.
14. Meyer J., Rowan B. Institutionalized Organizations: Formal Structure as Myth and Ceremony. In: New Institutionalism. Moscow: Idea-Press, 2010.
15. Hamel G., Prahalad K. Competing for the Future. — M.: Olimp-Business, 2002.
16. Cotter J. Leadership and Change. — M.: Alpina Publisher, 2014.
17. Giddens E. The structure of society. - M.: Academic project, 2005.
18. Foucault M. To supervise and punish. — M.: Ad Marginem, 1999.
19. Luhmann N. Social systems. — M.: Logos, 2007.
20. Hofstede G. Cultures and organizations: programming the mind. — St. Petersburg: Piter, 2016.
21. Pfeffer D. Power in Organizations. — Moscow: Alpina Publisher, 2018.
22. Scott W. Institutions and organizations. — M.: Logos, 2007.
23. Shane E. Organizational culture and leadership. — St. Petersburg: Piter, 2012.
24. Taleb N. Antifragility. — M.: KoLibri, 2014.
25. Polani M. Personal knowledge. - M.: Progress, 1985.